

To Study the Effect of Covid Diagnosed Working and Non-Working Women on Their Level of Emotional Maturity

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ABSTRACT

Background: Emotional Maturity gives us strength in fighting with all adversities and calamities calmly in life as well as increases the understanding of one's self concept and emotions and also provide insight about others emotions and behavior. It provides us proper stability in our life. **Aim:** As COVID-19 pandemic, affect the every dimension of life very adversely. Therefore, the aim of present research is to find out the difference between COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity. **Method:** Taking null hypothesis and Ex-post facto research was conducted by taking quota- sampling of 60 COVID diagnosed women, among them 30 are working women and 30 are non-working women. "Emotional Maturity Scale", by Dr. Yashvir Singh & Dr. Mahesh Bhargava[1] tool is applied for conducting the research. For statistical analysis t-test is applied and taken significance level at 0.05. **Result:** t-value came out to be 5.27, null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. **Conclusion:** To conclude we can say that working women diagnosed with COVID are more emotionally matured than non working women diagnosed with COVID.

Keywords: COVID diagnosed working & non-working women and Emotional maturity.

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INTRODUCTION

Emotional Maturity gives us strength in fighting with all adversities and calamities calmly in life as well as increases the understanding of one's self concept and emotions and also provide insight about others emotions and behavior. It provides us proper stability in our life. The Covid-19 pandemic has changed every dimension of our lifestyle i.e. the way we think, the way we feels, the way we behaves and work. During pandemic women played major role as a mother, caregiver, frontline workers, in academics, they diagnosed with covid-19. Usually in Covid-19 pandemic women suffered more than men in various areas in workplace i.e. health and social sector as well as home with excessive workloads due to lockdown and quarantine policies. Guo et al. [2] examined that Covid-19 positive patients suffered from higher levels of depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress symptoms as compared with negative patients, among them women significantly more "Perceived Helplessness" as compared to men.

Acharya [3] revealed that "a woman is the goddess of art and emotion, man has a concentration of courage and endurance. A complete personality emerges only upon combining the two". Mucci et al. [4] investigated that "during any crises, be it health or economic or environmental people tend to suffer an increased level of stress, anxiety and other psychological problems that threaten their overall wellbeing". Acharya [3] revealed that "21st century is the women's century". Now, during the 21st century women are coming out from their prejudiced and traditional area of work and entering into the male dominated field with the increase in liberty and educational awareness, women's stereotypes role and status are changing drastically. There holistic empowerment is taken into consideration by government and many organization as well.

During 21st century women can be categorized into working section and non working which are housewives for working outside women need to make many socio-familial adjustments that may resulted in more stress and anxiety. For working women, the important aspect of social and emotional changes is problem of stress. In today's era women have more opportunities to pursue their higher degree and knowledge, also started taking up the job opportunities outside their homes as well. But they are supposed to maintain cultural norms and values for this they have to make an adjustment with the family members. As per the data analysis during Covid-19 by Hao et al. [5] found that women have a higher prevalence of risk factors known to intensity during a pandemic including chronic environmental stain

preexisting depressive and anxiety disorders and domestic violence. Women performance reported by Aldrich and Lotito [6] reported that women leader's management is better than male in communicating pandemic policies.

According to Menninger [7] examined that "emotional maturity includes the ability to deal constructively with reality". Manzo [8] studied that during pandemic, women facing the full time responsibilities of care giving and homes schooling and Power [9] investigated the Covid-19 pandemic has increased the care burden of women.

Covid-19 pandemic affected lives of both working and non working women, both faces physical, environmental, emotional and mental trauma. Pandemic is affecting our mental strength, wellbeing and other holistic aspects of life adversely. Wide area of studies conducted on the impact of Covid-19 on women health but research was not conducted on the emotional maturity level of working and non working Covid-19 diagnosed women. This topic is becoming the chief concern of many researchers in the field of psychology. While understanding the significance of the topic researcher want to study the emotional maturity of working and non working women diagnosed with covid-19.

Research Problem

This present study also starts with a problem, which generates a curiosity in researcher mind. The proposed research was carried out through following one formal research questions:

1. Is there any effect of COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity?

Aim & Objective

To see the effect of COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity.

Hypothesis

In present research, researcher formulated the following null hypothesis for empirical verification:

H₀: There is no significant difference between COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity

Research Gap

Various study have done on emotional maturity and COVID relation, Loneliness perceived by elderly people during COVID, anxiety and depression related to COVID, but not a single study have conducted on COVID diagnosed working and non-working on their level of emotional maturity. Therefore, researcher wants to see the effect of COVID diagnosed of working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity.

Variables in Present Study:

METHODS

Methods of research provide tools and techniques by which research problems are investigated, thus the purpose of the research is to find answers to questions through scientific process applications.

Inclusion Criteria

In this research, researcher have included subject of age group 25 to 50 years of only women those are working and non working COVID diagnosed. Subjects in this test are post- COVID diagnosed women who are actually well and now their test is negative. Usually all women in the test diagnosed with COVID 3-4 months ago. Here was strictly considered that in independent variable there must be working category of women and other must be doing household works in the house not outside or not received any income for their household work i.e. non-working women.

Exclusion Criteria

In this research, only women were taken men were excluded and maximum 25 to 50 years women were taken in the research study, here elderly women and below the age group of 25years old excluded. Because according to the age emotional maturity of the women may affected or varied due to experiences in life. Usually as the age increases emotional maturity trend to be influenced positively.

Research Design

A research design is basically the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified created to seek answer to research question. For the present research work researcher used Ex-post facto design used or the data were analyzed and proper statistical techniques used.

Sample & Sampling

A sample of 60 participants (30 COVID diagnosed working women and 30 COVID diagnosed non-working women of age group between 25 to 50 year) were selected for the present research. The sample was selected to match the study and help in achieving the purpose of the study. Researcher has used quota-sampling technique for the data collection.

Research Tool

In the present study, Researcher used Emotional Maturity scale developed Dr. Yashvir Singh & Dr. Mahesh Bhargava.

Data Collection Procedure

First of all studying about the literature review and analysis the research gap decided about the variables i.e. emotional maturity, working and non working women diagnosed with COVID. For this study appropriate questionnaire "Emotional Maturity Scale" was selected. For data collection sample size of 60 was selected with the help of Quota sampling technique and Google form created for collecting online sample because of the spread of Covid-19 pandemic. 30 COVID diagnosed working women and 30 COVID diagnosed non-working women taken for conducting comparative study. Further scoring of the questionnaire calculated and with help t-test as a statistical analysis tool result was formulated. After this all level of confidence was checked, interpretation and discussion were done then at last, conclusion was given.

Statistical Techniques

In this study over a variable i.e. Emotional Maturity. The research work is conducted on COVID diagnosed working women and non-working on their level emotional maturity. Researcher used t-test is used for statistical analysis.

RESULT & INTERPRETATION

Collected data through above-mentioned inventories were analyzed in terms of mean, standard deviation and t-test method. The results have been presented in the tables.

H₀: There is no significant difference between COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity

H_a: There is significant difference between COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity

Comparison the level of social maturity between COVID diagnosed working women and non-working women

Groups	N	Level of Social Maturity		SE _D	t-value	Significance Level
		Mean	SD			
COVID diagnosed Working women	30	93.33	32.92	8.830	5.27	Significant at 0.05 level
COVID diagnosed Non-working women	30	139.83	35.43			

df =58

On the basis of the result table and graph, the mean of the Working women COVID diagnosed are 93.33 and the Non- working women COVID diagnosed are 139.83. The SD of the Working women COVID diagnosed is 32.92 and the Non- working women COVID diagnosed are 35.43. The t-test statistical was used to assess the significance mean of the null hypothesis. In addition, the t-value calculated is 5.271. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

During present scenario an emotional state and mental health is vastly influenced by the Covid-19 pandemic. Emotional maturity refers to ability to understand, and manage our own emotions as well as of others also. Emotional maturity enables to create the actual life we desire. Dosanjh [10] said that, "Emotional maturity means a balanced personality. It means ability to govern disturbing emotions, show steadiness and endurance under pressure and to be tolerant and free from neurotic tendencies". Emotional maturity also gives us strength in fighting with the adversities of the life and developing the altruistic behavior during covid-19 pandemic.

The aim of the present study is to find out the effect of COVID diagnosed working and non-working women on their level of emotional maturity. From the result table mean of the working women are 93.33 and non- working women are 139.83. The SD of the working women is 32.92 and non- working women is 35.43. The SEM of working and Non-working women diagnosed with covid-19 is 6.01 and 6.47 respectively. By the conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be extremely statistically significant; it is significant at 0.05 levels. Which indicates that working women diagnosed with covid-19 are more emotionally stable and matured as compared to the non-working women because the mean of the working women are less than Non-working women which shows that Non working women are unstable and working women are moderately stable Hence, our hypothesis is disproved and we can say that there is significant difference in the level of emotional maturity between the working and non working women diagnosed with covid-19 pandemic. Vaghela [11] found that working women significantly differ on emotional maturity score as compared to non-working women, working women have show better emotional maturity compared to non-working women.

In this research, researcher calculated the emotional maturity by considering five factors such as emotional instability, emotional regression, social maladjustment, personal disintegration, lack of independence. Emotional instability refers to rapid, often exaggerated changes in mood, where strong emotions or feelings (uncontrollable laughing or crying, or heightened irritability or temper) occur. These very strong emotions are sometimes expressed in a

way that is not related to the person's emotional state, working women can able to balance emotional state as compared to non-working women diagnosed with covid-19. Regression is the reaction we have when something happening in the present moment triggers a memory of something that occurred in the past – usually during childhood. It indicates emotional openness of a person. Emotionally unstable person is unable to cope up with emotional regression. Social maladjustment indicates the non adjusted behavior in a society which is not according to norms or law; emotionally matured persons are more socially adjusted. In the factor of personal disintegration which means lack of self understanding and adjustment. The last factor lack of independence shows dependency on others, lack of self consideration and decision making power, and all such factor indicated the level of emotional maturity between working and non-working women diagnosed with covid-19. As per the result emotionally matured persons are not emotionally unstable, regressive, social maladjusted, personal disintegrated and lack of independent. Mankani & Yenagi [12] conducted study to analysis the mental health of working and non- working women on the influence of socio economic status. The results indicated that the working women had better mental health when compared to non-working women. Chavda [13] investigated on the emotional maturity and mental health among working and non-working women for this taken. Result indicated that there is a significant different in emotional maturity and mental health of working and non-working women and also there was positive co-relation between emotional maturity and mental health in this we can say that if emotional maturity decreases than mental health also decreases and vice versa. From this research we can also say that emotional maturity affect the mental health of an individual and Maturity is based in responsibility; mature people live with higher levels of happiness and lower levels of depression and stress.

The emotionally mature turn their happiness into sharing and generosity. They offer helpful services to others as a way to spread their own wealth and joy in ways that circle back. Hence, on the basis of above result we can interrelated that subjects those who are working women diagnosed with covid-19 are more emotionally matured than the non working women diagnosed with covid-19.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that, working women diagnosed with COVID still more emotionally stable in the adverse condition, emotional non regression, social non maladjustment, personal integration and sense of independence. Emotional maturity gives us strength in self understanding and fighting calmly with adversities. Emotional maturity also plays great role in ones mental health, resilience power, personality an attitude. Basically our holistic health is affected by emotional maturity.

After completing the whole study, the result obtained reveals that there is significant difference between working women and non-working women diagnosed with covid-19. Hence, to conclude we can say that working women diagnosed COVID are more emotionally matured as compared to Non-working women diagnosed COVID.

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